

Use of recycled phosphorus products in organic farming in EU member states: Theoretically supported but practically restricted

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ABSTRACT

Organic farming policies and guidelines actively promote sustainable farming practices emphasising tighter nutrient cycles on farms and regionally. The European Union Green Deal aims to increase organic farmland to 25% and has triggered more discussion about nutrient supply challenges in organic farming, including propositions to allow the use of more recycled phosphorus products. Via a pivotal regulatory shift, struvite was allowed for use in organic farming in 2023 but dynamics involved in adoption of this recycled P product into organic farming are not understood. This study explores the influence of policy, technology, and financial instruments on the availability, accessibility, and adoption of wastewater-based struvite in organic farming. We use a qualitative multi-methods approach and adopt a systems perspective to explore the complex interplay between key sectors and the important variables in the recycled P chain. Our analysis reveals a lack of perceived P supply risk for organic farming in the European Union. Whereas the organic farming regulation is an arbiter for inputs into organic farming, adoption of recycled P products by farmers hinges on rigorous quality assurance and financial accessibility. Moreover, there are opposing views among actors on forms of policy interventions to facilitate availability and adoption of recycled P products in organic farming. However, within existing policy frameworks leverage points are present for strategic pathways to promote recycled P use in organic farming.

1. Introduction

Organic farming is purposely designed to promote sustainable practices, which includes nutrient circularity (Rahmann et al., 2017; Sanders et al., 2023). Organic farming policies and guidelines promotes closing nutrient cycles, soil health, limits off-farm nutrient inputs and emphasises reliance on biologically active soils for nutrients (Nowak et al., 2015; Seufert, et al., 2017a). Under Annex II of the EU organic farming regulation, several recycled nutrient sources including composts, meat and bone meal and digestates are approved (Ohm et al., 2017; Cooper et al., 2018; Möller et al., 2018). On farm nutrient cycling is an important feature for nutrient supply in organic farming but spatial decoupling of livestock and crop production has disrupted this flow and contributes to phosphorus (P) scarcity on arable farms (Foissy, et al., 2013; Cooper et al., 2018; Reimer et al., 2023a). Moreover, there are tight restrictions on production processes and composition of recycled nutrient resources for organic farming, which leads to limited practical

use on farms (Seufert, et al., 2017a; Cooper et al., 2018; Eyhorn et al., 2019). Approximately 80 % of recoverable societal P sources including food waste from retail and processing industry, incineration ashes/slugs, sewage sludge, and urine are completely prohibited in organic agriculture in the EU due to restrictive policies and contamination concerns, limiting a significant P recovery and recycling potential into the farming system (Kirchmann and Ryan, 2004; Oelofse et al., 2013; Möller et al., 2018; Løes, 2016).

The aim to increase organic farmland to 25 % by under the European Union (EU) Green Deal has triggered more discussion about the nutrient supply challenge in organic farming in the region (Purnhagen et al., 2021; Reimer et al., 2020). Among other suggestions to address this challenge in organic farming, are several propositions to lower restrictions and allow more recycled P products in organic farming in order to enable sustainable expansion of the farming system and increase yields (Nowak et al., 2013; Oelofse et al., 2013; Løes et al., 2017; Reimer et al., 2023a). In addition to potentially providing more nutrients

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to organic farming, recovering and recycling P is one of the fundamental ways to contribute to P circularity and circular economy (Loes et al., 2017; Withers et al., 2018). Intentional recycling; reintroduction of nutrients into the agricultural system requires support by diverse actors including public-organisations, private companies, policy makers, consumers and regulators (El Wali et al., 2019; Aarikka-Stenroos et al., 2023). These actors include waste management sector, fertiliser producers, P and agricultural policies, and farming representatives and farmers (Nedelciu et al., 2019a; Lyon et al., 2022).

Several variables shape actor engagement in intentional and strategic nutrient recycling (Aarikka-Stenroos et al., 2023). Among these, technology, financial investment, and policy are identified as priority factors for advancing P recycling efforts (Metson and Bennett, 2015). Legislative and regulatory frameworks are essential for stimulating innovative strategies for P circularity, yet need to be coupled with a streamlined shift towards advanced technologies that support efficient nutrient recovery and recycling which require substantial financial investments (Mehar et al., 2018; Nedelciu et al., 2019a; Aarikka-Stenroos et al., 2023; Walsh et al., 2023). A shift in policies without strategic measures and financial investments and technologies to support system changes can threaten agricultural productivity and food security (Manullang, 2022; Walsh et al., 2023). The approval of struvite as a recycled P source under EU regulation 2023/12 marks a pivotal shift, as it is currently the only sewage sludge-derived product permitted for use in organic farming across the EU. This regulatory advancement represents a significant step towards integrating more recycled P products into organic farming. However, dynamics involved in the adoption of this product into organic farming are not well understood.

Policies, technological advancements, and financial instruments each play crucial roles P recycling affecting stages such as recovery of P sources (de Ruijter et al., 2015), transportation of recycled material (Metson et al., 2020), steering reuse of nutrient-rich material (Barquet et al., 2020) and consumer choices (Eyhorn et al., 2019). Sector specific siloed approaches to addressing these critical variables to P circularity creates challenges for effective recycling, as the significance and impact of the different variables for facilitating or hindering actor engagement in nutrient circularity and circular economy differ across sectors (Barquet et al., 2020). To effectively address the availability, accessibility, and adoption of recycled P products, an understanding of how policy, technology and financial variables operate within and across sectors is essential (Mayer et al., 2016; Walsh et al., 2023). Therefore, to promote the availability and use of more recycled P products into organic farming, a cross-sectoral lens in the adoption of recycled P products in the organic farming system is necessary.

The main question of this study is: how do policy, technology and financial instruments enable or constrain the availability, accessibility and adoption of recycled P products in organic farming. We adopt a systems perspective to capture a comprehensive understanding of the financial, technology and policy tools influence on different sector's contribution to recycled P products use in organic farming. Fertiliser producers, wastewater treatment plants (WWTP) and organic farmers are essential to the availability, accessibility and adoption recycled P products and can be conceptualised as a P recycling system, where according to Lyon et al. (2020)'s adaptation of Checkland and Poulter (2006) system roles:

- a. The wastewater sector performs control functions that influences the availability of recycled P sources;
- b. Fertiliser companies perform as both producers and distributors of the recycled P fertilisers;
- c. Organic farmer representatives represent the decision-makers who decide, whether or not the products are adopted, depending on both their preferences and regulatory stipulations;

The boundary of a recycled P system was set mainly to the recycling of wastewater struvite into organic farming in the EU, given it's recent

addition to the list of allowable inputs. This substance, and the evolution of its use, can act as an indicator for how other recycled P products further down in the food production-consumption chain may be utilised in the future. To achieve the overall goal of the study, we combined semi-structured interviews a survey, and a policy review to capture the complex interplay between key sectors and the important variables.

2. Materials & methods

2.1. Study Design overview

This study is situated within critical realism which allows focus on both structural factors such as policy frameworks for P management and contextualised actor perspectives on various factors that enable or constrain their respective contribution to recycled P (Stutchbury, 2022). Furthermore, a critical realist approach supports inductive and deductive approach to data analysis, allowing us to identify and include variables that were not initially considered, but reflect underlying mechanisms and provide valuable insights to the topic understudy (Fletcher, 2017; Stutchbury, 2022).

To explore the multifaceted influences of different variables on the use of recycled P products in organic farming, we applied a multi-method data collection approach that combined semi-structured interviews, surveys and policy reviews (Alejandro and Zhao, 2024). The survey provided a farm-scale view on organic farmers' perceptions and attitudes towards recycled nutrient products. Semi-structured interviews with participants from fertiliser producers, wastewater treatment plants, organic farming sector; organic farmers, experts/representatives and organic farming policy, allowed in-depth exploration of sector-specific approaches, challenges and opportunities to P recycling for organic farming. Lastly, the policy review analysed the institutional framework that shapes P management in the EU and its applicability to P recycling for organic farming. Synthesising data from each method, we adopt systems thinking to understand the enabling or constraining aspects of different variables in one sector and how they interrelate with variables in other sectors, revealing key sectoral dynamics (Meadows, 2009). This approach allows in-depth analysis of the interconnected roles of the actors and considers their distinctive, similar or deviant perspectives regarding the influence of priority variables on recycling P into organic farming (Iacovidou et al., 2021).

2.2. Survey data

The survey data used in this study was collected to better understand nutrient use in organic farming by Reimer et al. (2023). From the survey, we extracted questions that examined which values influence conversion to organic farming (question B1), farmgate nutrient balances (question B5), and acceptance of recycled P products for analysis (question B9; Annex 1). The survey was conducted between October 2018 and June 2019. It was designed by the second author of this paper and distributed by in-country organic farming experts in seven European countries (Denmark, Italy, Germany, Hungary, Estonia, United Kingdom, and Switzerland). From the 84 organic farmers that participated, 80 provided responses to the questions considered in this study and the data was used to explore and quantify the receptivity of organic farmers to recycled P products.

We used descriptive statistics from the survey responses to highlight the factors that farmers consider to convert to organic farming and to show the number of participants willing to use various recycled nutrient products. Furthermore, we cross-tabulated to show the variables that influenced farmers' decision to either adopt or refrain from using recycled P products.

2.3. Expert interviews

2.3.1. Participants Recruitment

Key informant experts from organic farming, fertiliser production, the wastewater sector, and researchers were selected through purposive sampling. This sampling method allows for assembling of people that have demonstrable experience in specific fields (Etikan, 2016). Participants were found through Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam environmental geography networks, ReCaP (Horizon 2020, No. 95645), RELACS partners, online searches and some through conference programs. Data collection was approved by the ethics review committee of the Science faculty of Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam (Annex III). We aimed to interview individuals with a comprehensive understanding of the way sectors contribute to P circularity, knowledge of measures that have contributed to actors' effective contribution, or variables that hampered their efforts to recycle P. Consequently, all participants were individuals in senior positions and have at least 10-year experience in their respective fields. In total, we interviewed 23 experts (response rate = 45.8 %). From those, 4 belonged the fertiliser-producing industry, 6 to the wastewater sector, 9 to organic farming (one from EU organic farming policy) and 3P researchers. Despite our efforts, no individual from fertiliser producers that produce specifically for organic farming agreed to participate. Participants were from seven EU countries, six of which are north-western EU countries (Netherlands, Denmark, Germany, Hungary, Estonia, Sweden and Austria) or from a branch of an international company that is in the EU region. Data saturation was determined when there was data redundancy during the interview data collection, no more participants were contacted for interviews.

2.3.2. Interview set up

We developed a semi-structured interview guide with four themes:

1. Use or production of recycled P fertilisers/sources,
2. Perspectives on actors roles within the recycled P chain,
3. Influence of different variables on each actors' role
4. Interactions with other actors in the recycled P chain.

The interviews were designed to probe for how components of the different variables enable or constrain each sector's contribution to P recycling and the use of recycled P products in organic farming (Table 1, Annex 1). All interviews were conducted by the first author. The interviews were 45–60 min each, carried out from November 2022 to January 2024, and were conducted in English but none of the participants or the interviewer had English as their mother tongue. With the participant's consent, the interview sessions were audio recorded.

Table 1
Analytical themes and their descriptions for interview analysis.

Initial themes	Theme	Description	Results
	Financial	Financial resources needed by any of the actors to effectively participate in the recycled P chain.	Section 3.2.
	Political	Influence of existing policies on the actor's ability to participate in P recycling.	Section 3.1.
	Technology	Policies that are needed to facilitate more contribution of the sectors to P recycling. Processes used to recycle P. Current technologies that are essential in P recycling. Potential improvements on the current methods.	Section 3.3.
Emergent themes	Quality assurance EU supply	Importance more research to ensure quality standards. Perspectives on P supply risk to the EU.	Section 3.4. Section 3.5.

2.3.3. Interview coding and analysis

After the interviews were conducted a summary of the participants' most salient perspectives was written to take note of the variables that were at the fore front for each interviewee. Thereafter, the interviews were transcribed verbatim using Microsoft word dictate function, manual correction and then the transcripts were coded in atlas.ti. Interview data were coded deductively and inductively focusing for elements that enabled or hindered P recycling into organic farming under the preset themes while allowing for more themes to emerge. Through inductive analysis, two more variables; P risk supply and quality assurance of recycled P products were identified as significant to the actors' contribution to availability and adoption of recycled P products in organic and were therefore added as new themes. The framework method was used to systematically organise data according to the preset and emergent themes facilitating comparison of views across actors (Dixon-Woods, 2011). Then we adopted a system perspective lens (DeLaurentis and Callaway, 2004; Meadows, 2009) to interpret cross-sectoral perspectives on the constraining and enabling components of the priority variables highlighting the interconnections and various ways in which aspects of these variables influence the use of recycled P products in organic farming.

2.4. Policy review

To better understand the influence of regulatory tools on the availability and management of P and recycled P products in organic farming, we carried out a targeted search for the governance initiatives that affect nutrient management and P circularity in the EU. We searched the European Commission website (https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/research-area_en) for documents and initiatives that aim to promote nutrient/P circularity. We conducted the search by using keywords "phosphorus management", "phosphorus circularity", "nitrogen and phosphorus pollution" "nutrient circularity" and "agriculture pollution". This yielded a document titled "Systematic Approach to Preventing Pollution Nitrogen and Phosphorus" that contains a consolidated list of policy initiatives for nutrient management, from the European Commission website and cross referenced it with governance frameworks listed in Kalpakchiev et al. (2023). The EU commission summary lists eleven policy initiatives that aim to improve overall environmental sustainability at EU level. Thereafter, we used the hyperlinks in the document to read the specific policies and we selected six of the eleven listed polices (Table 2) based of their relevance of their objectives to the subject of this study.

The selected documents each include at least one objective or goal stating nutrient loss prevention, nutrient circularity and/or sustainable management. These documents were analysed through a word-based content analysis (Martin et al., 2014). Following an initial review and identification relevant objectives within the selected policy documents, we established a set of keywords for a manual word-based content analysis; "recycling", "recovery", "phosphorus", "nutrients", "nitrogen", "pollution", "soil", "agriculture", "organic agriculture/farming". Thereafter used the "find" and "Ctrl F" functions to search the keywords on the PDFs of the policy documents. The identified terms were then contextualised to understand the qualitative or quantitative targets set for nutrient and/or P recovery, and the underlying rationale for nutrient recovery and recycling. The word-based content analysis also allowed us to identify the prioritisation or lack thereof of organic agriculture within polices aimed at nutrient management in the EU.

3. Results

Our analysis provides a complex picture in which multiple variables influence availability, accessibility and use of recycled P into organic farming. It confirms the crucial importance of technology, policy and financial tools in P recycling. We also identified two additional variables influencing recycled P availability and usage in organic farming

Table 2
Policy initiatives that have potential to influence P recovery & recycling for agriculture.

Policy initiative	Aims/Plans	Specific document titles
Urban wastewater treatment directive (UWWTD) (revised in 2022)	To protect the environment from the adverse effects of urban wastewater discharges and discharges from certain industrial sectors. Revised objectives include: To lead to a more circular sector.	Council Directive 91/271/EEC of 21 May 1991 concerning urban wastewater treatment
The Nitrates Directive	To protect water quality across Europe by preventing nitrates from agricultural sources that pollute ground and surface waters and by promoting the use of good farming practices.	Regulation (EC) No 1137/2008
The common agriculture policy	Contribute to climate action, to protection of natural resources and to halting and reversing biodiversity loss. Lower support of mineral fertiliser use.	Summary of CAP Strategic Plans for 2023–2027: joint effort and collective ambition
The EU soil strategy	To reduce nutrient losses by at least 50 %, the overall use and risk of chemical pesticides by 50 % and the use of more hazardous pesticides by 50 % by 2030.	EU Soil Strategy for 2030 Reaping the benefits of healthy soils for people, food, nature and climate SWD (2021)
The integrated Nutrient management plan (INMAP)	To develop EU, nation and region specific action plans for nutrient management.	Nutrients – action plan for better management
Zero pollution	To improve soil quality by reducing nutrient losses and chemical pesticides use by 50 %.	Pathway to a Healthy Planet for All EU Action Plan: 'Towards Zero Pollution for Air, Water and Soil'
Fertiliser Product regulation (Regulation 2019/1009)	Facilitate internal market for bio-based nutrient sources.	Regulation (EU) 2019/1009 – the Fertilising Products Regulation

(Table 1). The enabling or constraining significance attributed to each variable varies among the actors (Table 2), and perspectives on different variables not only influences that particular sector but also shapes its interrelation with other variables in other sectors.

3.1. Enabling and constraining policy aspects

3.1.1. Organic farming regulation

Interviews and survey participants from the organic farming sector stated that organic farmers adhere to the regulations of the EU organic farming regulation and report that livestock manure, except from factory farming, contributes significantly to nutrient inputs for most organic farmers.

“So for phosphorus containing nutrients, yeah, we made a kind of exception and but you can only use it when the normal manure is not sufficient. So there must be a reason.” (Policy).

“You’re allowed to use conventional manure when it’s not made from factory farms. Which is interpreted differently by different Member States...” (Organic farmer representative 5).

Organic farmer representatives suggested that it is impractical to consider recycled P products that are currently not allowed under the EU organic farming regulation. The interviewed experts emphasise the importance of the regulation in maintaining the integrity of the organic

farming system. However, fertiliser producers reported that the precautionary principle of organic farming regulation is a main constraining variable to creating products for organic farmers.

“This is the legislation, I mean. Organic farming. There are some requirements and limitations that do not allow you to introduce fertilisers and...Lot of components.” (fertiliser company 3).

Furthermore, the interpretation of the organic farming regulation is decentralised, allowing member states discretion to setting national compliance standards for farming inputs. Fertiliser producers state the national variation in compliance standards hinders the production of recycled P fertilisers for organic farming since aligning production processes with multiple regulatory standards increases complexity and limits scalability.

“Organic farming in one country even within the EU is not the same like organic farming in the next country on a different association, it complicate the production process.” (fertiliser company 1).

In view of this, fertiliser producers propose that the regulation be revised and the narrow precautionary principles be reconsidered. Fertiliser producers argue that the existing regulatory framework and member-state guided implementation constrains their ability to invest into production of fertiliser products tailored for organic farming.

Although struvite is allowed for use in organic farming under regulation 2023/121, wastewater treatment plant actors did not exhibit awareness of specific standards or lack thereof required for compliance with organic farming practices. Moreover, they did not demonstrate understanding of how the organic farming regulation may constrain or enable their contribution to struvite production for organic farming.

3.1.2. Legislative framework for P recovery

Wastewater sector experts interviewed in this study all highlighted that the lack of EU wide legislation for P recovery and recycling is the main barrier to the sectors’ effective contribution to availability of recycled P sources.

“Phosphate recovery is something we do, but it’s not our main business. That’s not something in the legislation, that is not incorporated yet in the EU legislation. Perhaps it will be included soon because in Germany they already incorporated that...” (WWTP 2).

The policy review also shows that there are no EU wide quantifiable targets for P recovery or recycling in any of the initiatives aimed at promoting nutrient management. However, under the revised UWWTD (Table 1) there is an aim to operationalise the policy to facilitate recovery of P and N. Furthermore, as a complement to the EU soil strategy and UWWTD, the INMAP (Table 1) also seeks to stimulate market demand for recycled P products, potentially increasing accessibility of recycled products to organic farming, albeit still lacking quantified targets. Participants from WWTP argue that legislating P recovery would inadvertently reshape the financial prioritisation of the recovery facilities and necessitate skills required for efficient recovery, thereby potentially reducing the influence of financial limitations on both the wastewater sector and farmers.

“Nobody is willing to pay for us to do that and nobody is requiring us to do that... since it’s not a law that we have to abide to.” (WWTP 1).

These participants stated that since there is no regulatory structure for P recovery, there are no required recovery targets thus leading to uncertainties regarding supply to fertiliser companies.

“We should be a reliable producer. We cannot say the message this month no, this month we don’t have enough. Or the reactor is not working this month.”(WWTP 3&4).

Wastewater sector interview participants detailed suggestions for policy interventions. Participants propose a regulation mandating minimum quantity of recycled P into all fertiliser production portfolios and introducing of price ceilings to allow competitive advantage for recycled P products and promote adoption by farmers. They argue that these interventions could facilitate adoption through addressing the financial risk and return-on investment concerns further enabling the sectors’ contribution to the availability and accessibility of recycled P products

to agriculture.

In contrast, fertiliser producers reiterated that policy interference is not necessary for the demand and uptake of recycled P products because market dynamics will prevail.

“I don’t think that policy would need to intervene. So it’s...I’m not looking for them to say “it is a must that let’s say recycle and X amount” or they put any kind of higher taxes if you would use rock phosphate. So I would rather that they would not do anything and just leave it to the market, I think the market will go there.” (Fertiliser company 2).

While fertiliser producers and wastewater sector have opposing views on policy intervention regarding recycling quantities and pricing, they have somewhat similar views on the potential of regulatory measures to ensure quality of the recycled product. Fertiliser producers stated that regulatory monitoring could focus on ensuring that received products are trace elements and pollutants free, emphasising the importance of quality assurance for fertilising products, particularly to safeguard their reputation and ultimately foster consumer trust. Wastewater sector actor stated,

“So basically we put it in the bag and I take it under my arm to a company say well “here it is”. And the company says, “yeah, well, it’s not in this in the right size or it is too wet or do you have pathogen check”... we need policy for all of that...” (WWTP 5).

Existing policy initiatives (Table 1) address P mainly as a pollutant, and its management focused on curbing environmental challenges. Out of the six initiatives (Table 1), only one mentions organic farming in the context of sustainable nutrient inputs; common agriculture policy (CAP). The fertiliser product regulation, through promoting internal market for biobased fertilisers, has potential to limit the influence of national disparities for organic P sources between countries with nutrient surpluses and deficits. However, organic farming experts state that due to the prohibition of nutrient sources from factory farming under EU organic farming regulation and the lack of uniform definition of factory farming across EU member states, the utility of the fertilising product regulation within organic farming is limited and revisions are needed to be fully applicable. Nonetheless, struvite is allowed for use under the fertiliser product regulation, an enabling aspect of this policy initiative to the availability and access of recycled P products to organic farming across the EU.

3.2. Financial enablers and constraints

The financial variable is viewed as a crucial factor by all actors. In the fertiliser production sector, profits are the primary incentive to commence or continue contributing to the P recycled chain. Participants from this sector stated that expenses related to the transportation of secondary P material, particularly lower quantities strongly impact the feasibility of incorporating recycled P in fertiliser production, thus limiting their contribution to the recycled P chain. Furthermore, they postulate that integrating recycled P sources will likely reduce P output per hour. However, reiterate that producing recycled P products hinges on existence of viable market.

“So we can make the normal fertilisers based on the rock phosphates. But we can easily go to these other sources and then we have more sources. And we can easily do that, so...meaning we can make those products, we can produce those products, but if there’s no demand for them, yeah, we will not” (Fertiliser Producer 2).

In the wastewater sector (WWTP), participants stated that financial investments are required to develop new technologies and upscale existing ones to enable efficient production of struvite. This includes more investments in research and pilot studies that refine the production of recycled P products. Both the waste sector and fertiliser producers stated that recycled P products exhibit substantial marketing potential due to the widespread demand for sustainability among consumers. This underscores the imperative for these products to maintain a minimal environmental footprint, which aligns with the organic farmers’ values on environmental stewardship.

A majority of farmers in the survey ($n = 44$, 53 %) rate low input costs as a component that is moderately to very important on their decision to convert to organic farming (section 3.4, Fig. 1). Out of the $n = 32$ (40 %) of the organic farmers that are not willing to use meat and bone meal despite its approval by organic farming regulation, 38 % ($n = 12$) report higher prices as the main deterrent. The importance of financial accessibility to enable adoption of recycled P products was further corroborated by experts during the interviews.

“...and the price is reasonable. This is really actually very important question, if it is very high expensive product then they just don’t buy it. Because we have also, many commercial products on the market, but most of them are really expensive. Farmers just don’t buy them because they are too expensive.” (organic farmer representative 1).

3.3. Technological enablers and constraints

The wastewater sector and fertiliser producers participants all stated that these sectors have to adapt methodologies to optimise contribution to the recycled P chain. Fertiliser producers stated that integration of recycled P material into fertiliser portfolios requires modifying production lines, which is a cumbersome and administrative undertaking for complying with Registration, Evaluation, Authorization and Restriction of Chemicals. Within the wastewater sector, participants stated that they have functional reactors and have produced struvite, this is an enabler to the availability of this product to organic farmers particularly because there are no additional treatments to struvite for use in organic farming. However, WWTP participants also stated that they need to collaborate with fertiliser producers for including struvite into fertiliser portfolios, marketing and distribution. They highlight the absence of EU wide P recovery policy and lack quantified struvite production targets or quality standards hindering investments into efficient technologies, and creating inconsistent quality criteria for distribution to different fertiliser producers thus limiting the sectors’ contribution to recycled P availability.

“...And we have to change a little bit more because we expect that the company buys it from us. But the company also demands something from us. They demand a reliable producer of the struvite with constant quality. The promised volume...” (WWTP 4).

“Recovery plan is not a technique that WWTP are for...it is not the primary objective of WWTP, therefore the skills and technologies required to do it with high efficiency are missing.” (WWTP 5).

In other words, integrating P recovery is considered a fundamental change for a WWTP, from a treatment facility to a production facility. Furthermore, WWTP participants reported that the mechanics that can optimally recover P from wastewater are either under pilot studies or under development. They state that while struvite production from WWTP is beyond the pilot scale and is being implemented at larger scales, enabling its availability, only 25–27 % of phosphate in the wastewater can be recovered through precipitation.

“Even if you do the optimal operation of these reactors, there is no technology that is able to even produce half of what was promised by the technology providers, it’s still, it’s developing the technology” (WWTP 4).

Therefore, policy shifts that can trigger technological innovation are required to facilitate efficient struvite products and enforce quality standards.

3.4. Quality standards

Organic farming interview participants identified the organic farming regulation as the key framework overseeing input approvals into the farming system. However, they also highlighted that regulatory approval of a product for organic farming does not necessarily ensure its adoption by farmers. Interview participants highlight that quality assurance of recycled P products is paramount to adoption of these recycled material. More than 50 % of survey participants (Fig. 1)

Fig. 1. Factors that are considered important for transitioning to organic farming, on a Likert scale of 1–5, one being not important and five being very important. X-axis = number of participants and y-axis = factors considered.

reported that environmental friendliness is a very important factor for converting to organic farming. For struvite specifically, organic farmer representatives stated that more research and quality assurance is required to ensure there are no trace elements and the product truly meets the requirements for use in organic farming.

Survey results show that a majority ($n = 59$, ~75 %) of organic farmers are opposed to using sewage sludge-based products and only a few ($n = 7$, 9 %, Fig. 2) cited regulatory restrictions as a reason for reluctance. More than 50 % of the participants cited the possibility for contamination as a main concern deterring them from considering wastewater based recycled P products. This further emphasises the quality assurance and aligns with the prioritisation of environmental conservation and ecological considerations by organic farmers (Fig. 1).

Researcher participants in the interviews also echoed the need for more research for quality assurance, finetuning P recycling, and to optimise the efficiency of existing recycling technologies and recycled P sources. They also highlight that more research and knowledge dissemination is required to show the capacity of soils to neutralise contaminants stating, “Soils are also able to degrade and stabilize a lot of contaminants and that is not always taken into account” (Researcher 1). Such finetuning thus may also facilitate farmers’ willingness to adopt recycled P products.

3.5. Enabling and constraining influence of the supply risk perspective

Policy initiatives are designed to promote sustainable P management but none explicitly address the issue of P supply risk to the EU. These instruments present P management and recovery primarily as a solution to environmental challenges associated with P pollution. All interviews

participants across sectors understand the global P challenge and the physical scarcity of P rock in the EU. They also voiced the importance of nutrient circularity, particularly to reduce pollution and the environmental footprint of food production. However, they do not consider the relevance of P-supply challenges proximal to the EU or recognise this as a risk to the region’s food production.

When asked about the P supply challenges in the EU, a participant stated,

“Of course we have a limitation of the natural source of phosphorus. So one day it will be over. Not in the very close future. I will not be alive then anymore. Maybe in 300 years, I don’t know what the expectations are, but one day it will be over.” (Fertiliser company 1).

Organic farming policy participant affirmed this perspective on P supply, for organic farming, suggesting the inclusion of struvite in organic farming guidelines was largely driven by its availability from wastewater treatment plant rather than the demand for new P sources in organic farming.

“I know that elsewhere in the world there is a lack of manure, a lack of inputs, in Europe I do not think that is the case, maybe some parts of some countries. But I do not think there is a risk of lack of supply anywhere in Europe...” (Policy).

In the survey, 42 % ($n = 18$) of organic farmers who reported their P budgets $n = 43$ (54 % of the total participants) reported negative budgets but are still opposed to using sewage sludge based recycled P products. Organic farmer representatives presented diverse perspectives on the significance of P as a challenge for organic farming in the interviews. Some interview participants ($n = 3$) stated that they primarily perceive N as a potentially limiting factor, while those who acknowledge P also argue for the inclusion of other macro and micronutrients in the

Fig. 2. Willingness to use recycled P sources; Y-axis = types of P sources, x-axis = number of participants.

discussion. Nonetheless, these participants also recognise that systematic changes are necessary for sustainable food production under increased farmland area.

“it will be impossible to have 25 % organic farmland without revising allowable inputs into organic farming” (farmer representative 3 & 6).

They suggest focusing on the efficient distribution of agricultural products, food waste reduction and exploiting legacy P in agricultural soils instead of exploring alternative inputs. The views on EU agricultural P supply from all sectors, coupled with lack of specific recovery and recycling measures into agriculture on the policy documents constrain the contribution of these sectors to the availability, access and adoption of recycled P products into organic agriculture.

4. Discussion

4.1. Implications of the supply risk perspective

Across the sectors considered in this study, there is a common understanding for the need of sustainable P management. Actors demonstrated understanding of the importance of reducing nutrient pollution. This unanimity among sectors has also been observed in a global study by Greiger *et al.* (2024). Furthermore, significant financial investments; EUR 370 million, have been made to P and N research in the EU, focusing on nutrient cycles and pollution, fertiliser production, efficient use in agriculture and governance since 2017 (EU Commission, 2023). The academic understanding of nutrient challenges and actor perspectives on the importance of P sustainability, are an enabling factor for potential respective contribution to P recycling.

Survey results show that some farmers experience negative P budgets, consistent with findings from previous studies (Ohm *et al.*, 2017; Le Noë *et al.*, 2018; Reimer *et al.*, 2020). Despite this, interview participants from the organic farming sector do not perceive urgency that necessitates incorporating more recycled P products into organic farming. This lack of urgency is corroborated by WWTP participants

who did not observe increased struvite demand after its approval for use in organic farming, indicating limited adoption by organic farmers. Participants from other sectors also do not perceive P supply risk proximal to the EU. This perception is also reflected in the legislative tools that mainly emphasise P management for environmental protection and have no quantifiable targets to reintegrate recovered resources into agriculture. This approach to P management is not unique to the EU; in Canada (McCourt, *et al.*, 2024), USA (Drohan *et al.*, 2019) and China (Li *et al.*, 2021) frameworks to facilitate P management also mainly address P as a pollutant. Greiger *et al.* (2024) attribute the lack of urgency regarding P supply to a comparatively high financial accessibility to P resources in regions such as EU. This underestimation of long-term phosphorus challenges among many stakeholders could be due to the delayed manifestation of P deficits in crop yields (Mishra *et al.*, 2024). The lack of perceived urgency act as a critical barrier to the broader adoption of recycled P products like struvite and advancing sustainable P management practices within organic farming since perceived supply risk is important for triggering policy actions and an increase in adoption of products through regulatory legitimacy (Nedelciu *et al.*, 2019b; Colombo *et al.*, 2024). A more integrated approach to P management is still needed to address P scarcity in organic farming and explore governance synergies that optimise recovery and reuse. Furthermore, collaborative knowledge development is needed to bridge the disconnect between the academic understanding of P management and the practical perspectives of organic farmers.

4.1.1. Availability of recycled P products

While the EU has some of the most progressive policy initiatives (Table 3) and has recycling and recovery technologies aimed at facilitating P circularity, significant challenges persist (Carrillo *et al.*, 2024). Previous studies have identified a gap in P governance at both global and EU scale (Brownlie *et al.*, 2021; Garske and Ekardt, 2021; Kalpakchiev *et al.*, 2023). Struvite use in organic farming is permitted under the fertiliser product regulation granted it meets the requirements set in

Table 3
Summary of the prioritisation of different variables.

Variables	Salient views	Actors to which its most relevant
Policy	Lack of P recovery policies.	WWTP
	Need for policies that steer recycled P product demand.	WWTP
Finance	Organic farming regulation.	Organic farming
	Financial investments into recycling technologies.	WWTP
	Availability of viable markets.	Fertiliser producers
	Importance of profits.	Fertiliser producers
Technology	Reasonable pricing/financial accessibility.	Organic farmers
	Lack of more efficient reactors.	WWTP
	Low investment in research required to upscale or introduce new methods.	WWTP
Quality assurance	Need for more research and data to ensure sufficient quality standards.	Organic farmers & researchers
	Understanding of P physical scarcity in the EU.	All actors
EU supply	EU P supply risk is not proximal to the EU.	All actors
	EU organic farming does not have a P supply. Problem.	Organic farming

Regulation (EU) 2019/1009 of the European Parliament and council, similarly to other livestock based nutrient sources, animal manure as a source must not originate from factory farming (European Sustainable Phosphorus Platform, 2023). No specific characteristics for organic farming are specified in the regulation, but instead specific physico-chemical characteristics for the product to be used as a fertiliser are specified. The majority of the operational plants meet these requirements (Muys et al., 2021; European Sustainable Phosphorus Platform, 2023). Industrial-scale struvite recovery technologies from different technology providers are operational at various wastewater treatment plants across the EU, enabling the availability of recycled P products (Muys et al., 2021). This includes; NuReSys, SUEZ, Ostara, Colsen, Veolia and CNP Cycles. However, the WWTP actors also note the absence of EU wide specific P recovery legislation posing a substantial barrier to the wastewater sector's effective contribution recycled P source availability. Using a subsistence flow analysis to study the Swiss P system dynamics since 1989, Mehr et al. (2018) shows that policy has capacity to increase P recycling and P use efficiency. Therefore, targeted policy instruments are needed to ensure stable production and enhance the market competence of recycled P sources.

The wastewater sector advocates for an EU-wide P recovery regulation and offers additional recommendations for advancing P recycling, drawing on established frameworks in other environmental sectors to enable adoption. For example, as an enabling factor, integrating recycled P into all fertiliser production portfolios to stimulate demand mirrors the approach of the Renewable Energy Directive, which mandates bioethanol inclusion in fuel to promote renewable sources. Using existing sustainability frameworks in P management has also been suggested by Metson et al. (2022), who introduces the concept of net-zero P cities. This underscores that P management and reintroducing P into the agricultural system does not require to "reinvent the wheel" (Metson et al., 2022). Similar mandates, such as the Renewable Energy Directive, may increase demand and incentivise investment in recycled P production, as observed in the USA with the implementation of Renewable fuel standards and the partial success of National policy of Biofuels in India (Das, 2020; Kumar & Verma, 2024). However, influence of similar strategies to the availability and accessibility of recycled P products to organic farming is uncertain given the technical challenges stated by the WWTP interviewees. Furthermore, the quantity of wastewater based recycled P has been shown to be insufficient for P demand of major crops in some countries in the EU (Serrano-Gomez et al., 2023). Perhaps, alongside proposing instruments to promote adoption by

organic farmers and ensuring quality assurance, should be an exploration of the extent to which these products can meet the current and future P demand in organic farming.

4.1.2. Accessibility & adoption of recycled P products

Availability of recycled material such as struvite and predisposition about environmental conservation and impact in organic farming are enablers for adoption of recycled products (Kumagai, 2020; Polyportis et al., 2022). Furthermore, struvite has been shown to be an effective fertilising agent for grain crops (alfalfa and wheat) in organic farming (Thiessen Martens et al., 2022). However, to facilitate adoption by farmers, identifying and using strategic points of intervention within existing policy initiatives is necessary. Within the organic farming regulation framework and EU nutrient management policies such as the fertilising product regulation, and Nitrates directive, there are leverage points to facilitate the use of recycled P products in the farming system. The livestock-to land ratio in Art.14 of organic farming regulation focuses on livestock rearing considering avoiding overgrazing, soil compaction and erosion; this can influence P management, paralleling how the Nitrate Directive limits manure P application in nitrate vulnerable zones (Amery & Schoumans, 2014). Reducing stocking density is also part of the broader objectives of the Farm to Fork strategy under the Green Deal. Low stocking densities, distance between specialised farms and dependence on legume crops for biological N fixation are associated with low manure P input and negative P budgets in organic farming (Nelson and Janke, 2007; Nowak et al., 2015; Reimer et al., 2020). This would likely enhance the required need for struvite in addressing P requirements for organic farming, especially because increase in organic farmland in the EU is projected to lead to increased legume production for N fixing properties (Barbieri et al., 2019). The use of struvite in organic farming could be coupled with the incentivised greening measures under CAP, from which organic farming is already benefiting from, and thus stir demand for the product.

Organic farmer representatives reiterated that quality assurance and financial accessibility is essential to the acceptance of recycled P products into organic farming. The differing perspectives on policy intervention between fertiliser producers and WWTP pose a constraining factor to accessibility and adoption of recycled P products, as WWTP actors view policy as essential for establishing price ceilings to promote accessibility to farmers. Ultimately, while policies can act as structural mechanisms to regulate compliance, practical implementation of recycling technologies and adoption of recycled P products by farmers are shaped by financial constraints. Financial constraints can be compounded by ideological concerns particularly around the perceived low solubility of struvite also limit adoption, despite scientific evidence, such as Kirchmann and Ryan (2004), indicating that solubility is not a major barrier to product quality. For quality assurance, more research, that highlights rigorous quality assurance for struvite and provide a clear cost effectiveness and environment benefits has been done. Struvite is the most studied recovered P product with high purity and low potentially toxic trace metals content (Shih et al., 2017; Zhou et al., 2015). However, Bünemann et al. (2024) highlights that although concentrations of contaminants in biofertilisers have decreased significantly over time in Europe, concerns about contaminants still create doubts among organic farmers for adoption of such products. Yet, participants reiterate need for more research for quality assurance. This suggests a knowledge gap between state of the art research and its practical use and understanding. This can be attributed to the non-linear relationship between academic research and practice which requires intentional knowledge dissemination and transfer (Reed et al., 2021; Dwivedi et al., 2024).

5. Limitations

The implementation of the organic farming regulation which governs nutrient use in organic farming varies per member state meaning that the use of recycled P fertilisers also differ. Regularity alignment at

EU level is needed for effective P governance (Kalpakchiev et al., 2023). A framework to kickstart availability and adoption of more P sources i.e. P recovery legislation would need to be established at EU level and applied nationally. Therefore, while our results have limited geographical coverage, it nevertheless provides a general overview of enablers and constraints to use of recycled P products in organic farming in the EU. Furthermore, our results are largely consistent with previous studies on the potential use of recycled nutrients in agriculture.

6. Conclusion

There is a complex interplay between policy, technology, and financial variables in enabling and constraining the adoption of recycled P products within organic farming (Mehrer et al., 2018; Rose et al., 2022; Bünemann et al., 2024). While technological advancements such as industrial scale struvite recovery have increased the production of struvite, gaps in supportive legislative frameworks and financial incentives continue to limit its broader and reliable availability. However, existing P management and sustainable agriculture policies within the EU can be leveraged to promote accessibility and use of recycled P products into organic farming. The approval of struvite for use in EU organic farming under the Fertilising Products Regulation allowing EU-wide distribution, is a fundamental enabler for use of a recycled P product in organic farming. Further, the emphasis on environmental stewardship in organic farming presents a strategic pathway for promoting the environmental and agronomic benefits of struvite through targeted marketing. Nonetheless, broader adoption depends on increased demand from the

organic farming sector, a shift that may be impeded by fertiliser producers' resistance to policy interventions aimed at stimulating this demand. These findings underscore that coordinated policy and market strategies that align technological progress with financial and regulatory support are needed to foster an effective P recycling framework tailored to the unique goals of organic agriculture.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

S. Magaya: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Data curation, Conceptualization. **M. Reimer:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **G.S. Metson:** Writing – review & editing, Validation. **T-S. Neset:** Writing – review & editing, Validation. **M. Torralba:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **C.J.E. Schulp:** Conceptualisation, Writing - review & editing, Validation.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix 1: Survey questions

Questionnaire.

OB.1 Why did you choose organic farming? Please score the following potential advantages of farming organically, from 1 to 5, where 1 is not important, 2 is slightly important, 3 is moderately important, 4 is important and 5 is very important.

Higher price for output Reduces input costs .

Higher yield Improves soil fertility .

Better market Environmental benefits .

Health benefits Better Quality .

Other, please specify _____.

B. 2 Please score the following possible problems encountered when farming organically, from 1 to 5, where 1 is not important, 2 is slightly important, 3 is moderately important, 4 is important and 5 is very important.

Not enough manure Weed control .

Pest control Lack of labour .

Low yield Problem with price .

Lower quality Disease control .

Other, please specify _____.

B. 3 Have there been any unusual problems (drought, lack of market, diseases, pests...) with in the cropping seasons of 2015–2017? (Please state kind of problem and cropping season.).

2015: _____.

2016: _____.

2017: _____.

B. 4 In what ways has you overall farm nutrient management changed since you converted to organic farming in regard to nutrient management? Please describe how _____.

OB.5 a Do you think that you apply sufficient amount of fertilizer to your crops? Please explain [Note: please get the farmer to elaborate on why they answered as they did] _____.

B. 5b Does your farms rely on external inputs to fulfil the nutritional need?

Yes No .

B. 5c Do you think you can estimate your nutrient farm gate balance is for the following nutrients? (please answer in kg per ha and year).

N: kg ha⁻¹ year⁻¹ K: kg ha⁻¹ year⁻¹.

P: kg ha⁻¹ year⁻¹.

B. 6 What is the **main** reason for the use of external inputs?

Fulfilling nutrient needs of:

N P .

K S .

Humus Others (specify):

OB.7. Looking to the future, what do you think the main sources of nutrient inputs to your farm will be? Please explain:

OB.8. Where do you get advice from about how to manage nutrients on your organic farm? [Note: Please elicit as detailed information from the farmer as possible, including names of advisors (if the farmer is willing to share)]:

OB.9 View on recycling nutrients from organic waste streams: Please try to answer without regarding the current legislation on the use of recycled fertilizers!

a) In general, would you consider using recycled fertilizer on your farm?

Yes No .

b) Please fill in the table below about which recycled fertilizer you would consider using and which not. Also, please select a reason behind your decision.

Type of fertilizer	Municipal waste Compost		Digestibles (Biogas)	Champost	Sewage sludge	Sewage sludge products (struvite, ashes...)	Bone/meat meal and similar others
	household sourced	garden and park waste					
Would use?	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>						
Reason: Please note that main rationale for yes/no response							

OB.8. Are there any analysis results from soil samples? (possibly copies of reports / scanned reports) for the farm?

Notes:

Appendix 2. . Interviews guiding questions

Interview question themes	Questions	Goal
Institution/sector role	What is your company/institution do to contribute to P recycling or circularity. Can you tell me about your experience working in this field?	To understand what participants view as the role of the sector on P recycle chain.
Recycling (enabling factors)	Does the company use any recycled materials in production of fertilisers? Are any recycled P fertilisers used? What types of fertilisers are currently used in organic farming? Which recycled P sources do you produce? How long have you been producing struvite?	To understand their production, incorporation or use of recycled products
Actor perception	How can other sectors help promote or facilitate your efforts to contribute to P recycling and circularity?	How other actor influence the participants' contribution? What they view as the roles of other actors
Policy	What rules/policies have been helpful in ensuring that you produce/use recycled P products? What rules (policy/regulations) do you think have been limiting your use or production of recycled P products?	To understand policies that are perceived as influential on actors' contribution
Potentials	What needs to be done, politically or otherwise to facilitate your contribution to recycled P products use/production? Have other sectors have so far limited your contributions to P circularity.	Participants' perspectives on the optimal course of action or scenario for managing P beyond current constraints

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